

S3E – Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine

**PRESS KIT
OPEN CALL #1 PROMOTION**

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Abstract

The S3E press kit is an information pack that we have prepared for organisations and media that want to support the promotion of the S3E Open Call #1 and communicate the opportunity to potential beneficiaries about enrolling in tailored programs and services aiming at boosting the South European Deep Tech ecosystem. This document is suitable for all types of organisations.

Disclaimer

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1. The South3E project in a nutshell

The **S3E – Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine** project mission is to develop an **engine of growth** that will contribute to improve the connectedness and efficiency of the **entrepreneurship ecosystems in southern European countries**.

South3E is a joint initiative funded by the European Commission under the European Innovation Ecosystems SCALEUP call, part of the Horizon Europe Programme. The project will take 30 months and it will be managed by 4 partners from Portugal, Greece, Ireland and Spain. The team consists of experts from the research, innovation and acceleration ecosystem, together with policy and community building experts.

S3E will focus on accelerating **deep tech projects, start-ups, and SMEs** that, by providing solutions towards a more sustainable society and economy, can impact social development and economic growth in these countries and contribute to the timely achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, in line with the EU Green Deal, the Recovery and Resilience Facility and the Next Generation EU fund.

S3E will provide skills to researchers and technology transfer actors in science-based entrepreneurship and technology commercialization, supporting growth stage start-ups in business development and in procuring investment, and providing technology brokerage for corporates and scale-up stage start-ups and SMEs.

2. Information of the Open Call #1

On 7th November 2022, the consortium of S3E – Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine has **launched its first open call** as part of the development of an engine of growth that will improve the connections and efficiency of the entrepreneurship ecosystems in Southern European countries.

In the framework of this open call, the South3E project will develop disruptive solutions built around unique or hard-to-reproduce breakthroughs, and products, processes or services capable of fulfilling currently unmet (or ill-met) market needs. This new engine will **unlock the untapped innovation potential of Southern European deep tech**, targeting scientific and technical excellence in the fields of agriculture, natural sciences, health, engineering and technology.

The call is built around **three tracks** of bespoke services tailored to researchers and innovator's varying levels of maturity (i.e., early, growth, and scaling stages):

- **S3E Start:** For research teams and technology transfer offices, S3E offers a hands-on training program to hone their commercial skills and secure early funding for development.
- **S3E Charge:** For growth start-ups, S3E provides mentoring and networking to develop an investment-ready business plan and facilitate access to non-dilutable and dilutable funding
- **S3E Reverse:** For scaling start-ups and SMEs, S3E will set up an Open Innovation ecosystem to broker, connect and match corporates to scaling start-ups through a challenge-solution duality.

Applicants must submit a project envisaging an economic and social impact, targeting one or more of the following Sustainable Development Goals:

- **No Poverty (SDG 1):** End poverty in all its forms everywhere.
- **Zero Hunger (SDG 2):** End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.
- **Good Health and Well-Being (SDG 3):** Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.
- **Quality Education (SDG 4):** Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.
- **Gender Equality (SDG 5):** Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.
- **Clean Water and Sanitation (SDG 6):** Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.
- **Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7):** Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all.
- **Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8):** Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
- **Industry Innovation and Infrastructure (SDG 9):** Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
- **Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10):** Reduce inequality within and among countries.
- **Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11):** Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable.

- **Responsible consumption and production (SDG 12):** Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.
- **Climate Action (SDG 13):** Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
- **Life below water (SDG 14):** Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development.
- **Life on land (SDG 15):** Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.
- **Peace, justice and strong Institutions (SDG 16):** Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.
- **Partnership for the goals (SDG 17):** Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development.

The deadline for applying to the S3E Open call is 10 February 2023, 17:00 CEST.

To obtain more information about the application form and detailed guidance for applicants, please visit the project website: <https://south3e.eu/apply-now/>

3. Social media channels

When promoting the S3E project and the S3E Open Call #1, it is of outmost importance to tag @South3E and use tailored hashtags. These are the S3E social media channels and hashtags that must be used:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/south3e/>

<https://twitter.com/south3e>

It is also important to always refer to the S3E website

<https://south3e.eu/>

#Hashtags:

[#SustainableS3EU](#)

[#EntrepreneurshipEngine](#)

[#South3E](#)

[#DeepTech](#)

[#S3Eopencall](#)

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4. Graphic material

The S3E consortium has prepared the following **visuals in English for you to download** and promote the S3E Open Call #1:

S3E Graphic material (press kit)

- [Visual for Twitter](#)
- [Visual for LinkedIn](#)

5. EISMEA Press Release

The European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) published a press release informing about the opening of the S3E Open Call #1. Check it out here:

[Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine \(South3E\) project: first call open for research teams, start-ups and SMEs](#)

6. S3E Press Release

A press release published by the S3E team announcing the open call can be found here:

[S3E Press Release Open Call 1](#)

7. One pager

A one pager presenting the project in a nutshell, its objectives, activities and partners can be found here:

[S3E one pager](#)

8. Partners involved and social media profiles

S3E consortium partners are:

- [HiSeedTech](#) - A not-for-profit association founded by private companies that came together with the purpose of enabling the creation of value from knowledge through technology entrepreneurship and open innovation.
- [EPLO Institute for Sustainable Development](#) – part of an international organization dedicated to mainstreaming the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the EU Green Deal, providing capacity building, policy work and educational programs.
- [IDI](#) (International Development Ireland) specialises in practical day-to-day implementation for Government agencies in economies which are growing and changing rapidly
- [Australo](#) Interinnov Marketing Lab SI - is a marketing agency specializing in growth hacking for research and innovation.

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Consortium Partners	@AustraloTeam	@Australo
	—	@HiSeedTech
	@eplo_news	@EPLO European Public Law Organization
	—	@International Development Ireland
EU organisations	@EU_Commission	@European Commission
	@HorizonEU	—
	@EUScienceInnov	@EU Science, Research and Innovation
	@EU_HaDEA	@European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)
	@REA_research	@European Research Executive Agency (REA)
	@DigitalEU	@EU Digital & Tech
	@EITeu	@EIT - European Institute of Innovation and Technology
	@EUeic	@European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA)

Institute for Sustainable Development

INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IRELAND

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